

THE INVESTIGATION OF SUBMISSIVE BEHAVIORS AND SELF-RELIANCE LEVELS OF MOUNTAINEERS

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Abstract:

This study was carried out in order to determine the submissive behavior and self-confidence levels of individuals who practice mountaineering sports. While the population of the study was individuals participated Erzurum Winter Development Camp in 2015, the sample of the study was consisted of 212 participants (n=169 male, 43 female) selected by random sampling. A 3-part questionnaire was used to collect data in the study. In the first part of the questionnaire, there is a 16-item "Submissive Behavior Scale" (SBS) to determine the submissive behavior levels of the participants. In this part of the questionnaire, "Self-confidence Scale" of which validity and reliability study was performed by Akın (2007). The last part was allocated for 7-item 'Demographic Information Form' developed by the researcher to learn the demographic information of the participants. The data were analyzed with SPSS packet program. Besides the descriptive statistics, T-test and ANOVA were utilized and Tukey test was used to specify the groups from which significant differences were derived and Pearson correlation test was used in order to examine the relationship between variables. Findings have shown that mountaineers, living in rural areas, have lower self-confidence than the urban and metropolitan residents. Additionally, the confidence of the athletes in the alpinist was higher than in other branches. Besides, it was found out that there existed negative relationship between submissive behavior and self-confidence.

Keywords: mountaineering, submissive behavior, self-confidence, sport

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1. Introduction

The individuals doing mountaineering make their movements by estimating what the natural life offers. The knowledge, skill acquisition, mental and physical achievement, decision-making and experiences of the mountaineers are the components of the nature of this sport. The rapid spread of urbanization causes people to have problems meeting their needs of living in touch with nature. This is the one of the reasons why nature sports become widespread recently (Koçak and Balcı, 2010). Besides its physical difficulties with the difficulties for the adaptation to natural life conditions, mountaineering, which is the most known of nature sports, requires psychologically strong individuals (Ulker, 1992).

Gürün (1991) defines the submissive behavior as thinking and acting according to demands of authority by being affected psychologically, cognitively and emotionally and following the rules of authority. These kinds of behaviors have been diversified as feeling compelled to abide by the decision of others, abstaining to say no, having difficulties to express thought and anger even under negative circumstances, showing no sagacity to uphold the rights (Gilbert and Alan, 1994). Similar human behaviors form at the end of "common learning" processes starting at early ages and going through a life time. Submissive behaviors in interpersonal relations, in another word, confusion between respect and obedience, it is seen that obedience is referred as "respect" (Kağıtçıbaşı, 2008). It is observed that individuals showing submissive behaviors have difficulties to behave freely, feel confirmation all the time, tend to accept the situation not to have problems even they are accused of anything in which they are not wrong (Yıldırım, 2004). The weakness of initiative aspect of these individuals and being unable to show leadership behaviors (Özkan and Özen, 2008), existence of socialization, risk-taking and challenging in the nature of mountaineering (cited from Carr in Gürer et al., 2006) create a contradiction between mountaineering and submissive behaviors. Factors such as socialization, risk-taking and challenging are related to individuals' self-confidence directly. In this point, self-confidence terms should be examined.

Self-confidence is the judgment to feel valuable (Bandura, 1997), being aware that individuals can create control and domination on their own world (Karademir, 2015). Concept of self-confidence is divided into two aspects impending internal and external. While internal self-confidence is a condition about one's self, external self-confidence involves relationships of people with the environment (Akin, 2007).

Sport has mental and social contribution besides its physical benefits (Yarımkaya et al., 2014; Zorba, 2012). One the factors affecting success in sport is self-confidence (Yıldırım, 2013). Taylor and Wilson (2005) explained the belief of athletes in their abilities to be successful in terms of self-confidence. Considered the probable risks in

mountaineering (Gürer et al., 2006), dealing with these risks requires high level of self-confidence.

People have to make decisions and develop their skills in natural life. Internal self-confidence related to climbing activities and external self-confidence related to camping activities show the importance of self-confidence for mountaineering (Graydon and Hanson 2005).

In the direction of given information, submissive behaviors and self-confidence of mountaineers have been examined and answers for following questions have been sought:

- Do submissive behaviors of mountaineers differentiate according to demographic variables?
- Does self-confidence of mountaineers differentiate according to demographic variables?
- Are there significant relationship between self-confidence and submissive behaviors of mountaineers?

2. Methods

2.1 Study Model

This was a descriptive study, which was conducted by using survey method. Survey studies have been using commonly in social science and these are the studies which are conducted on wide groups, opinions and attitude of the members of these groups. Any taken cases and events are tried to describe (Karasar, 2005; Karakaya, 2011).

2.2 Population and Sample

169 male and 43 female, totally 212, athletes participating Erzurum Winter Development Camp consisted the sample group. Most of the participants were male (79.7%). Athletes of 35 year-old and over were the largest group (42.5%). Approximately three quarters of the participants were graduated students (73.1%).

The most of the participants having income almost equal reported that they lived in metropolis (62.3%) of the participants defining themselves mostly as "Alpinist" (83.5%), those having sporting background less than 3 years were low (9.4%).

2.3 Data Collection Tool

A. Personal Information Form

Demographic information of participants was determined by using "demographic information form" designed by the researcher. The form has 7 questions including age,

gender, educational status, income, living environment, the sporting branch they defined themselves and sporting background.

B. Submissive Behaviors Scale

Submissive Behaviors Scale was developed by Gilbert and Allan (1994) based on the study of Buss and Craik in 1986. The adaptation of the scale was conducted by Savaşır and Şahin (1997). The scale having 16 items and 0.89 of reliability coefficient is 5-point likert type and the higher scores show the higher level of submissive behaviors. In this study, Cronbach's alpha value was found to be (0.83). In this study the adapted version of Submissive Behaviors Scale was used.

C. Self-Confidence Scale

Self-confidence scale, developed by Akın (2007) based on the self-efficacy theory of Bandura was used to assess self-confidence level of participants. 33-item scale consists of two subscales including internal self-confidence (17 items) and external self-confidence (16 items). While internal consistency value was $\alpha = 0,83$ for the whole scale which is 5-point likert type, it was $\alpha = 0,83$ for internal self-confidence and $\alpha = 0,85$ for external self-confidence (Akın, 2007). With the internal subscale, the information about which individuals know and love themselves, specifying clear goals can be acquired. Information about which a number of features such as relationships of individuals between social environment, abilities of self-expression and communication, controlling the emotions and risk-taking can be acquired in the subscale of external self-confidence. The score found by dividing the total score to item number (33) gives the information about individuals' self-confidence. The score under 2.5 refers to "Low Level", between 2.5 and 3.5 refers to "Mid-Level", over 3.5 refers to "High Level" self-confidence (Akın, 2007). In this study, Cronbach's Alpha value was found to be $\alpha = 0.93$.

2.4 Data Analysis

Collected data was evaluated in SPSS program. T test and ANOVA for independent samples, Tukey Post Hoc test for the determination of the differences between groups were used. The relationship between variables was analyzed by using Pearson Correlation Test. The significance of the results were evaluated in the level of $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

The results in this study have been given on tables and with explanation in this section.

Table 1: Demographic information of the participants

Gender	f	%	Environment Living in	f	%	
Male	169	79.7	Rural	7	3,3	
Female	43	20.3	City	73	34,4	
Age	f	%	Metropolis	f	%	
Under 20	16	7.5	Branch in Mountaineering	f	%	
21 – 25	51	24.1		Alpinism	177	83,5
26 – 30	29	13.7		Rock Climbing	27	12,7
31 - 34	26	12.3		Sport Climbing	6	2,8
35 and over	90	42.5		Long Wall Climbing	2	0,9
Educational Status	f	%	Sporting Background	f	%	
Middle School	6	2.8	Less than 2 years	20	9,4	
High School	22	10.4	3 – 5 years	66	31,1	
Bachelor Degree	155	73.1	6 – 8 years	41	19,3	
Master Degree	29	13.7	9 – 11 years	19	9,0	

Table 2: The mean scores of submissive behaviors and self-confidence of the participants

Dimensions	$\bar{X}$	S.D.
Submissive Behaviors	2.38	0.634
Self-confidence	4.09	0.489
1. Internal Self-confidence	4.11	0.522
2. External Self-confidence	4.07	0.496

The mean scores of submissive behaviors and self-confidence of the participants were given in table 2. Submissive behaviors mean of the participants was found to be low ($=2.38$). Self-confidence levels were found to be high ($=4.09$). ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: The relationship between submissive behaviors and self-confidence

Submissive Behaviors	Self-Confidence
Sig. (2-tailed)	-0.167* $p=0.015$

In table 3, it can be seen that there is negative low relationship between self-confidence and submissive behaviors. $p < 0.05$.

Table 4: Analysis of submissive behaviors according to gender

Dimensions	Gender	n	$\bar{X}$	s	t	p
Submissive behaviors	Male	169	2.39	0.65	0.582	0.561
	Female	43	2.33	0.55		

As it is seen in the table 4, no significant differences were found between genders in terms of submissive behaviors ($t=,582$, $p=,561$). ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Analysis of submissive behaviors level according to other demographic variables

Dimensions	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Age	Under 20	16	2.65	0.766	1.531	0.194	-
	21-25	51	2.43	0.596			
	26-30	29	2.46	0.726			
	31-34	26	2.35	0.520			
	35 and over	90	2.28	0.621			
Educational Level	Middle School	6	2.81	0.949	1.319	0.269	-
	High School	22	2.44	0.683			
	Bachelor Degree	155	2.34	0.579			
	Master Degree	29	2.45	0.788			
Environment living in	Rural	7	2.45	0.569	0.048	0.953	-
	City	73	2.37	0.660			
	Metropolis	132	2.37	0.627			
Branch they define themselves	Alpinism	177	2.36	0.632	0.673	0.570	-
	Rock Climbing	27	2.45	0.704			
	Sport Climbing	6	2.68	0.420			
	Long Wall Climbing	2	2.25	,088			
Sporting Background	Less than 2 years	20	2.47	0.542	1.379	0.242	-
	3 – 5 years	66	2.30	0.610			
	6 – 8 years	41	2.52	0.608			
	9 – 11 years	19	2.52	0.658			
	Less than 2 years	66	2.30	0.683			

It can be seen in Table 5 that no significant differences were found between demographic variables in terms of submissive behaviors ($p < 0.05$).

Table 6: Analysis of self-confidence level according to gender

Dimensions	Gender	n	$\bar{X}$	s	t	p
Self-confidence	Male	169	4.08	0.496	-0.082	0.935
	Female	43	4.09	0.468		
Internal self-confidence	Male	169	4.11	0.530	0.137	0.891
	Female	43	4.10	0.494		
External self-confidence	Male	169	4.06	0.501	-0.321	0.749
	Female	43	4.09	0.480		

It is seen in table 6 that there is no significant difference between genders in terms of self-confidence ($p < 0.05$).

Table 7: Analysis of self-confidence of the participants according to age

Variable	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Self-confidence	Under 20	16	3,89	,491	1,415	,230	-
	21-25	51	4,06	,490			
	26-30	29	4,23	,482			
	31-34	26	4,04	,517			
	35 and over	90	4,10	,479			
Internal self-confidence	Under 20	16	3,90	,520	1,506	,202	-
	21-25	51	4,05	,532			
	26-30	29	4,25	,533			
	31-34	26	4,06	,524			
	35 and over	90	4,14	,506			
External self-confidence	Under 20	16	3,88	,527	1,250	,291	-
	21-25	51	4,07	,474			
	26-30	29	4,21	,474			
	31-34	26	4,01	,543			
	35 and over	90	4,06	,496			

As it is seen table 7, no significant differences were found between age groups in terms of self-confidence ($p < 0.05$).

Table 8: Analysis of self-confidence of the participants according to educational status

Variable	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Self-confidence	Middle School	6	4.28	0.246	0.671	0.571	-
	High School	22	4.14	0.542			
	Bachelor Degree	155	4.06	0.483			
	Master Degree	29	4.14	0.523			
Internal self-confidence	Middle School	6	4.35	0.356	0.909	0.437	-
	High School	22	4.19	0.577			
	Bachelor Degree	155	4.07	0.514			
	Master Degree	29	4.16	0.547			
External self-confidence	Middle School	6	4.21	0.246	0.393	0.759	-
	High School	22	4.09	0.560			
	Bachelor Degree	155	4.05	0.488			
	Master Degree	29	4.12	0.534			

It can be seen in table 8 that no significant differences were found between educational statuses of participant in terms of self-confidence ($p < 0.05$).

Table 9: Analysis of self-confidence of the participants according to the environment living in

Variable	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Self-confidence	Rural	7	3.56	0.695	4.706	0.010*	1-2
	City	73	4.07	0.443			1-3
	Metropolis	132	4.12	0.489			
Internal self-confidence	Rural	7	3.51	0.756	5.281	0.006*	1-2
	City	73	4.09	0.473			1-3
	Metropolis	132	4.15	0.518			
External self-confidence	Rural	7	3.61	0.635	3.397	0.035*	1-3
	City	73	4.04	0.461			
	Metropolis	132	4.10	0.498			

As it is seen table 9, there are significant differences between environments participant living in. As the result of comparison analysis, the differences in total self-confidence and in subscales weigh against the participant living in rural. It is seen that self-confidence level of participant living in rural is lower than those living in city and metropolis ($p < 0.05$).

Table 10: Analysis of self-confidence of the participants according to branches

Variable	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Self-confidence	Alpinism	177	4.10	0.498	4.947	0.002*	
	Rock Climbing	27	4.19	0.320			4-1
	Sport Climbing	6	3.73	0.430			4-2
	Long Wall Climbing	2	3.01	0.021			
Internal self-confidence	Alpinism	177	4.12	0.533	5.409	0.001*	
	Rock Climbing	27	4.23	0.313			4-1
	Sport Climbing	6	3.67	0.386			4-2
	Long Wall Climbing	2	3.00	0.000			
External self-confidence	Alpinism	177	4.07	0.497	3.812	0.011*	
	Rock Climbing	27	4.15	0.416			4-1
	Sport Climbing	6	3.83	0.499			4-2
	Long Wall Climbing	2	3.03	0.044			

In table 10, it is seen that there are significant differences between branches that participants define themselves in terms of self-confidence. The athletes defining themselves as long wall climber have lower scores than other athletes in terms of total self-confidence, internal and external self-confidence ($p < 0.05$).

Table 11: Analysis of self-confidence of the participants according to sporting background

Variable	Category	n	$\bar{X}$	s	F	p	Difference
Self-confidence	Less than 2 years	20	4.09	0.473	0.741	0.565	-
	3 – 5 years	66	4.05	0.548			
	6 – 8 years	41	4.02	0.423			
	9 – 11 years	19	4.07	0.579			
	Less than 2 years	66	4.17	0.444			
Internal self-confidence	Less than 2 years	20	4.04	0.521	0.701	0.592	-
	3 – 5 years	66	4.09	0.597			
	6 – 8 years	41	4.03	0.445			
	9 – 11 years	19	4.13	0.618			
	Less than 2 years	66	4.18	0.457			
External self-confidence	Less than 2 years	20	4.14	0.469	0.993	0.413	-
	3 – 5 years	66	4.01	0.537			
	6 – 8 years	41	4.01	0.437			
	9 – 11 years	19	4.01	0.572			
	Less than 2 years	66	4.15	0.471			

No significant differences were found between sporting backgrounds in terms of self-confidence, as it is seen in table 11

5. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study in which submissive behaviors and self-confidence levels of mountaineers were examined, athletes reported low scores in submissive behavior and high scores in self-confidence levels (Table 2). This result can show that individuals having these features tend to do mountaineering because nature sports involve concepts such as risk, challenge and being brave.

In another finding, negative correlation was found between self-confidence and submissive behaviors (Table 3). In their study in which self-confidence levels and submissive behaviors of physical education teachers against school administrators were examined, Cengiz et al. (2014) found significant relationship between self-confidence and submissive behaviors, even this level was reported to be low. Submissive behavior is defined as an obligation to comply with an authority and it is contradictory to expect someone having submissive behaviors to act creating and believing own authority like it is two people in one body. This contrast is parallel with results of this study.

No significant difference was found between demographic variables (table 5). This result can show that athletes having particular level of physical and psychological toughness took place in the education camp selected as the study field. Koç et al. (2010)

found submissive behaviors of university students in mid-level. These results support our findings.

When the findings of self-confidence were examined, it was found that the environment participants living in had impact on their self-confidence levels. It was found that self-confidence level of participants living in rural was lower than those living in city and metropolis (table 10). This result could be a result of that athletes living in metropolises and cities might get the opportunities such as socialization, communication, self-education and development, which are affecting self-confidence directly or indirectly, because self-confidence is a changing process (Ekinci, 2013), it is possible that self-confidence can change in different periods according to environment in which athletes living.

The other variable in which self-confidence varied was branches defined by athletes. The athletes defined their branches as alpinism reported higher scores both in internal and external self-confidence (table 10). The reason for this result can be shown that alpinists are closer to the opportunities to socialize and that they participate group activities. Moreover, Alpinism includes high altitude activities such as tracking and hiking involving different walk style and long-period camping.

Especially, high altitude activities depending on environmental factors and climbing group include some risks such as climate, height, and pressure can be the factors affecting the level of athletes' self-confidence in this branch (Ponchia, Fattore, Tempesta, Thiene, Biasin ve Agostin, cited in Gürer et al., 2007).

Consequently, as it is seen in the study of Ekici and Kircan (2016) suggesting that nature sports camping has contributions to socialization of youth, it has been found that mountaineers have higher self-confidence and show generally no submissive behaviors. It was found that there was a low level of relationship between self-confidence and submissive behaviors of mountaineers. Self-confidence levels of mountaineers were found to be high according to their branches. The athletes defining themselves as long wall climber have lower scores than other athletes in terms of total self-confidence, internal and external self-confidence. The results of this study can guide researchers planning to do research into mountaineering.

References

1. Akin, A. (2007).The Development and psychometric Charecteristich of The Self-Confidence Scale, *Abant İzzel Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 7 (2), 167-176.
2. Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. New York: Freeman.

3. Cengiz.R, Arslan .F, & Şahin.E. (2014). Confidence and Submissive Behavior Evaluation of Physical Education Teachers, *Turkish Journal of Education TURJE*, 3,(3).
4. Don Graydon- Kurt Hanson (2005). *Mountaineering: The Freedom of the Hills (Çeviren Tunç FINDIK)*. Homer Kitap evi: İstanbul.
5. Ekici, S., & Kircan, T. (2016). Social integration of the individuals according to some variables who participated in Youth Camps of Ministry of Youth and Sports, *Journal of Human Sciences*, 13(3), 4906-4916.
6. Ekinci, S. (2013). The Investigation Self-Reliance Perceptions Related to Soloist Stage Performance of Music Teacher Candidates According to Variables, *Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 2(2), 52-64.
7. Gürün, O. A. (1991). *Psikoloji Sözlüğü*. İstanbul: İnkılap Kitabevi.
8. Gilbert, P., & Allan, S. (1994). Assertiveness, submissive behavior and social comparison, *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 33, 295-306.
9. Gürer, B., Savaş, H. A., Gergerlioğlu, H. S., Hazar, Ç. K., & Uzun, M. (2006). The effect of altitude on anxiety level during climbing mount Süphan *Genel Tıp Dergisi*, 17 (3), 161-166.
10. Kağıtçıbaşı, Ç. (2008) Human and Humans in Nowadays, *Introduction to Social Psychology*. İstanbul.
11. Karademir, N. (2015). Students Perception of Self-Confidence in Department Of Geography in Faculty of Science and Letters. *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 12 (1), 53-77.
12. Karakaya, İ. (2011). *Scientific Research Methods (2.Baskı)*, Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık.
13. Karasar, N. (2005). *Scientific research methods*. Nobel Publisher. Ankara, Turkey.
14. Koç, M., Bayraktar. B., & Çolak T. S. (2010). Investigation of Submissive Behavior in University Students In Terms Of Various Variables, 28(1), 257-280.
15. Koçak, F., & Balcı, V. (2010). The Environmental Sustainability in the Sporting Events in Nature. *Ankara Üniversitesi Çevre Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2 (2), 213-222.
16. Özkan, İ. A., & Özen, A. (2008). The Relation between Submissive Behaviours and Self Esteem State among Nursing Students. *TSK Koruyucu Hekimlik Bülteni*, 7 (1), 53-58.
17. Taylor, J. & Wilson, G. S. (2005). *Applying Sport Psychology: Four Perspectives*. Champaign, Ill.: Human Kinetics.
18. Savaşır, I., & Şahin, N. Ş. (1997). Bilişsel Davranışçı Terapilerde Değerlendirme: Sık Kullanılan Ölçekler. Ankara: Türk Psikologlar Derneği Yayınları.
19. Ülker, İ. (1992). *Mounteering Tourism*. T.C Ministry of Tourism publications. Ankara: Devran press.

20. Yarım kaya, E., Akandere, M., & Baştuğ, G. (2014). Effect of self-confidence levels of 12-14 years old students on their serving ability in volleyball. *Niğde University Journal of Physical Education and Sport Sciences*, 8 (2), 242-250.
21. Yıldırım, İ. (2004). Prevalence of Submissive Acts among High School Students. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 26, 220-228.
22. Yıldırım, F. (2013). Adaptation of Sport Trait Self-Confidence Subscale and Studying Sports Trait Self-confidence In Various Variables on High School Students. Mersin Üniversitesi Yayınlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi) Mersin, Turkey.
23. Zorba, E. (2012). *Sports for All*. Ankara: Neyir publishers.

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